

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

**Data Study
Group Final
Report:
SenSat**

9–13 December 2019

Semantic segmentation
of 3D point clouds

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3878499>

This work was supported by The Alan Turing Institute under the EPSRC grant EP/N510129/1

Contents

1	Executive summary	3
1.1	Challenge overview	3
1.2	Data overview	4
1.3	Main objectives	4
1.4	Approach	5
1.5	Main conclusions	5
1.6	Limitations	5
1.7	Recommendations and future work	6
2	Problem formulation	6
2.1	Task definition	6
2.2	Evaluation metrics	8
3	Data overview	9
3.1	Dataset description	9
3.2	Exploratory data analysis	10
3.3	Split of data	13
4	Methodology	15
4.1	PointNet	15
4.2	PointNet++	19
4.3	SuperPoint	21
4.4	KPConv	24
4.5	RandLA-Net	26
4.6	ConvPoint	29
5	Experiment results	31
5.1	Overall results	31
5.2	Detailed KPConv results	32
6	Future work and research avenues	40
6.1	Evaluation on Cambridge dataset	40
6.2	Instance segmentation	40
6.3	Data augmentation	41
6.4	Transfer learning	41
7	Team members	42

A List of all labels

45

1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

Autonomous vehicles require digital maps to navigate safely, smart cities requires knowledge of urban features to be managed appropriately, and digital twins require physical assets to be recognised before they can simulate predictive models. All those applications require a detailed representation and understanding of the spatial environment. The ability to create intelligent 3D models of the real world is a critical enabler for the reduction in cost and programme of major design activities. For instance, Highways England is one of the pioneers in developing parametric design solutions for complex national infrastructure.

SenSat captures high resolution images via drones with a ground sampling distance of ~ 2.5 cm. Those images are then transformed into 3D point clouds, using techniques such as Structure from Motion (SfM). The ability to understand point clouds and 3D shapes is critical for supporting the growing market of parametric design and various applications.

Photogrammetric point clouds are unstructured and unordered data representing the real world with XYZ and RGB values. Although visually rich, these point clouds have limited spatial context associated for algorithms to extract meaningful information. In order to extract the spatial context, techniques such as point cloud segmentation and classification is commonly explored. This allows computers to recognize the composition of the 3D scene. However, the lack of effective semantic and instance segmentation techniques is currently acting as a blocker in this industry.

This DSG intended to explore point cloud segmentation techniques, in order to recognise objects such as roads, buildings, cars, trees, and ground in a large 3D urban environment. This will enable safer autonomous vehicles on the road, automated asset management in urban planning, and accurate digital twin simulations.

3D point cloud segmentation and classification has long been a popular research topic. Earlier methods generally follow the steps of ground filtering, clustering, feature extraction, and supervised classification. Features can be extracted from individual points directly or from a cluster

of points, and then fed into a standard classifier. However, recent few years have witnessed exponential growth of 3D neural networks for point cloud understanding, such as PointNet, followed by PointNet++, PointCNN, etc. At the meantime, many benchmark data, both indoor and outdoor, became available to the research community, e.g., S3DIS, Scannet, Sematic3D, and recent Paris-Lille-3D. Since RGB information are available for point clouds generated by Structure-from-Motion, by incorporating RGB channels into the new networks, better results are expected.

The overall aim of this challenge is to investigate various semantic segmentation methods to discover how well they perform on outdoor large-scene urban area datasets. We also aim to find what are the limitations of the individual methods and how useful they are in practical problems such as the one considered within the challenge.

1.2 Data overview

The dataset provided by SenSat is in the form of 3D point clouds that describe objects in large-scale outdoor urban areas. Two datasets are available, one describing Perry Barr area of Birmingham, and the other one describing central Cambridge. Point clouds representation is the closest representation to the raw sensory data. However, point clouds are inherently unstructured, non-uniform and orderless. The standard convolution neural networks cannot directly be applied to this kind of data. In this dataset, each datapoint is represented by its X, Y, Z coordinates as well as its R, G, B colour values. The labels include items such as construction, street furniture or cars, and each data point has one of these labels. There are no label provided for distinguishing different instances of objects of the same class.

1.3 Main objectives

The main objectives are the following:

- Evaluate and compare several selected state-of-the-art methods for 3D point cloud semantic segmentation.

- Identify what modifications to existing methods are needed to make them work on the large-scale dataset.
- Identify what are the practical limitations of the methods and suggest how they could be improved.

1.4 Approach

We identified four state-of-the-art methods: RandLA-Net, KPConv, ConvPoint and SuperPoint as well as some iconic baselines: PointNet and PointNet++. We split labelled Birmingham data into training and validation data, and we used them to evaluate the selected models. We decided to try a variety of both advanced and simpler methods to identify how large improvement margins advanced methods gain compared to conceptually simpler methods.

1.5 Main conclusions

- Most methods such as PointNet, PointNet++, and Convpoint are unable to directly process large point clouds, due to their expensive sampling operation or memory-cost convolution.
- KPConv produced the best results in terms of both OA and mIoU. However, RandLA-Net achieved similar results with much less training time. This suggests that effective local feature aggregation and appropriate receptive field are important to the semantic segmentation of large-scale point clouds.
- Semantic segmentation of real-world large-scale point clouds is still a open challenge, mostly due to extremely imbalanced classes, for which a meaningful feature representation is difficult to learn.

1.6 Limitations

- Exploratory data analysis has shown that there is significant class imbalance within the data. Because of that, the models fail to learn some of the classes.

- We were able to do a very limited amount of hyperparameter tuning due to time restrictions. This limits the performance and prevents a fair comparison between the models. In an ideal case, each model would be tuned close to its optimum performance.
- The models were validated on data that are similar to the training data - part of Birmingham in the same area.

1.7 Recommendations and future work

- Evaluate the models on Cambridge dataset so that generalization abilities of the models are evaluated to a larger extent.
- To alleviate the problem caused by imbalanced data distribution, weighted cross-entropy, focal loss, and dice loss could be further used to improve the performance of these methods. Also, oversampling and under-sampling techniques could be further used to balance the data.
- Computationally and memory-efficient convolution operation directly on unstructured point clouds could be further investigated to tackle the problem of large-scale point clouds processing.
- To further study the pros and cons of the color features and geometric features, further ablation study could be conducted to see the difference.
- Post-processing steps such as conditional random field could be used to further improve the performance and refine the results.

2 Problem formulation

2.1 Task definition

In this challenge we focus on the task of semantic segmentation of 3D point clouds. Semantic segmentation is about identifying the class of each point in an image or 3D point cloud. We illustrate semantic segmentation in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Input image compared with the ground truth and prediction for semantic segmentation (extracted from Jordan 2018).

Semantic segmentation is closely related to instance segmentation. In instance segmentation, in addition to classifying the points we also identify to what instance the points belong. This allows us to count how many instances of a certain category there are. We compare semantic and instance segmentation in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Semantic and instance segmentation (extracted from Jordan 2018).

We only have labelled data for semantic segmentation, so we have not evaluated instance segmentation techniques. Potential ways how to do instance segmentation are included within future work section.

2.2 Evaluation metrics

There are two metrics that we use to quantitatively evaluate the performance of the models. The first of them is the overall accuracy of which the points are classified. The second metric is called Mean Intersection over Union (mIoU). The goal is to compare how different models compare in terms of these two metrics - larger value is better.

Overall accuracy is the proportion of points that were correctly classified. A weakness in using such accuracy is that it may be dominated by a few classes that have many examples. For example, predicting the most common class could easily lead to high accuracy if most examples belong to the most common class.

Intersection over Union is defined in the following way:

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{\text{target} \cap \text{prediction}}{\text{target} \cup \text{prediction}}$$

IoU intuitively measures how many points were classified correctly out of all points that either belong to a specific class or were predicted to be in a specific class.

To make it easier to understand the individual parts of the IoU formula, they are illustrated in Figure 3 and 4.

Figure 3: Comparison of the ground truth and the prediction (extracted from Jordan 2018).

Figure 4: Comparison of the intersection and union of the ground truth and the prediction (extracted from Jordan 2018).

3 Data overview

3.1 Dataset description

The data provided by SenSat describe large outdoor areas in two different regions - Perry Barr area of Birmingham (1.2 km^2) and central area of Cambridge (3.2 km^2). The first dataset was to be used for training and validation, while the second dataset was set aside for testing, which could be done with the best model after the data study group finishes. The datasets are stored as csv and las files. The structure of the data is $(X, Y, Z, R, G, B, \text{class})$.

There are 31 classes, which can be further merged into 13 more general classes, one of which is "Unclassified". The set of more specific classes includes, for example, construction stockpiles, fence, street furniture-benches or vehicles-cars. The more general labels include labels such as construction, street furniture or cars. For example, street furniture includes sub-classes such as benches, road signs, lamp posts, traffic lights and others. The full list of classes in both specific and general lists is in Appendix A.

There are also alternative datasets/benchmarks that are related and cover both indoor and outdoor areas. These include S3DIS, Scannet, Sematic3D and Paris-Lille-3D. But none of the data is representing the real world at a large scale with many types of objects as the test

data.

3.2 Exploratory data analysis

In order to have a better understanding of the given data, we analysed the labelled data set that covers a part of Birmingham. In particular, we visualized the whole area and how it is split into individual parts. Subsequently, we investigated the smallest part (part 5) in more detail and analyzed the distribution of classes in order to retrieve information on the class imbalance of the data set.

3.2.1 Visualization of the Birmingham data set

Figure 5 visualizes the whole area of the labelled data set. The area corresponds to an outer part of the city of Birmingham and consists of several prominent features, including a large construction site, a shopping mall with car park, large green areas, a stadium and many roads.

Figure 5: Visualization of the labelled data set of Birmingham. The point cloud is shown in true RGB color.

3.2.2 Individual parts of labelled data

As illustrated in Figure 6, the labelled data is split into five sub-parts which we will refer to as part 1 to part 5.

Figure 6: Illustration of the 5 subsets from the point cloud data set.

Part 5 is the smallest one, with a size of (x, y, z) : $200\text{m} \times 200\text{m} \times 28\text{m}$. Despite its small size it contains a wide range of classes which makes it adequate during the model preparation and for first training runs. Figure 7 shows a top view of part 5 from two slightly distinct perspectives.

Figure 8 shows a zoom on a small extract of part 5 in both RGB colors (*left*) and converted to gray scale (*right*). It can be nicely observed that the density distribution of the point cloud is strongly heterogeneous. In the shown example we can see that the roof of the house is well mapped while parts of the side walls are missing. We will see later that this strong data point density can have consequences on the performance of the model and that some models are less sensitive in regards to this data characteristic.

Concerning the class occurrences, part 3 contains the most complete class representation. For this reason we split part 3 in a eastern and

Figure 7: Top view of part 5. Here, to reduce the image size, only 10% of the points are drawn (evenly selected each 10-th).

western part in order to use them for training and for validation, respectively.

In the next section we will analyze in more detail the class distribution.

3.2.3 Distribution of classes

As a further important data exploration step we analyzed the distribution of classes which is shown in Figure 9 for all 30 classes from the original labeling. We can identify several dominant classes, including the ground, commercial buildings, vegetation as well as roads. Some of the classes have very few instances, such as bikes, traffic cones and construction stockpiles. Overall, there is huge class imbalance within the data.

After reducing the labels to 12 more general classes, class imbalance still persists. The dominant classes are unchanged and some classes have

Figure 8: Cropped area of part 5 ($30\text{m} \times 30\text{m}$) in original RGB (*left*) and converted to grey scale (*right*).

very few examples close to zero despite gathering several classes into a more general class. The distribution of general classes within the part 5 training and validation data set (see Figure 10) confirms the class imbalance similar to what we have observed across all parts.

3.2.4 Distribution of classes on the map

To understand the distribution of classes, we visualize the class distribution spatially. Similarly as before, we first considered the 30 specific classes and then looked at the more general classes. Figure 11 shows the spatial class distributions over the whole area of the data set. We see that the dominant classes often cover large continuous regions rather than many small parts.

3.3 Split of data

As seen above, the *Birmingham* data set is split into five smaller parts. Investigation has shown that part 3 includes labels that are not present in other parts. Consequently, we have decided to split part 3 into two smaller parts - one that is used for training and one that is used for validation.

Figure 9: Distribution of all 30 classes over the whole data set.

In summary, we used the following split of data during our experimental evaluation:

- **Train:** Parts 1, 2, 4, and 5 as well as the eastern subset of part 3.
- **Validation:** The western subset of part 3 (defined by easting coordinate less than 406484.3).
- **Test:** *Cambridge* dataset.

Figure 10: Distribution of the 12 general classes, left: training dataset, right: validation dataset.

Figure 11: Spatial distribution of the original 30 classes (*left*) and the relabeled general 12 classes (*right*) over the whole dataset of Birmingham.

4 Methodology

4.1 PointNet

PointNet, proposed by Qi, Su, et al. 2017, is a deep-learning based model for point cloud segmentation and classification.

Figure 12: Uses of PointNet (extracted from Qi, Su, et al. 2017).

4.1.1 Motivation and idea

PointNet is a unified architecture that directly takes point clouds as input and outputs either class labels for the entire input or per point segment/part labels for each point of the input. The basic architecture of our network is surprisingly simple as in the initial stages each point is processed identically and independently. In the basic setting each point is represented by just its three coordinates (x, y, z) . Additional dimensions may be added by computing normals and other local or global features. The key to the model is the use of a single symmetric function, max pooling. Effectively the network learns a set of optimization functions/criteria that select interesting or informative points of the point cloud and encode the reason for their selection. The final fully connected layers of the network aggregate these learnt optimal values into the global descriptor for the entire shape as mentioned above (shape classification) or are used to predict per point labels (shape segmentation).

The input format is easy to apply rigid or affine transformations to, as each point transforms independently. Thus, by adding a data-dependent spatial transformer network that attempts to canonicalize the data before the PointNet processes them, the results can be further improved.

4.1.2 Implementation

The main architecture of this method is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 2. **PointNet Architecture.** The classification network takes n points as input, applies input and feature transformations, and then aggregates point features by max pooling. The output is classification scores for k classes. The segmentation network is an extension to the classification net. It concatenates global and local features and outputs per point scores. “mlp” stands for multi-layer perceptron, numbers in bracket are layer sizes. Batchnorm is used for all layers with ReLU. Dropout layers are used for the last mlp in classification net.

Figure 13: Architecture of PointNet (extracted from Qi, Su, et al. 2017).

One important finding we noticed during the re-implementation is that the original segmentation task does not use two transformation networks depicted in the network architecture. The authors of PointNet didn’t specify this in their seminal work. However, it is easy to understand that for their task as they only have (x, y, z) coordinates. While for our task, with (x, y, z) coordinates and RGB values, the transformation networks do not have physical interpretation.

The segmentation network is an extension to the classification PointNet. Local point features and global feature (output of the max pooling) are concatenated for each point. No dropout is used for segmentation network. The decay rate for batch normalization starts with 0.5 and is gradually increased to 0.99. We use adam optimizer with initial learning rate 0.001, momentum 0.9 and batch size 32. We set the number of points for each example to be 4096.

4.1.3 Experimental setup

It is worth mentioning that PointNet is designed for indoor scenario and part segmentation, which both are a small-scale point cloud segmentation tasks (~ 4000 points per scene). For our task, the smallest scene has more than 2 million data points. We cannot directly apply PointNet to our

data.

One reasonable solution is to partition each scene into small square regions based on (x, y) coordinates. Compared with PointNet's task, we enlarge the area by 4×4 . The data points in each small region is different. The distribution of the data points can be dense (e.g. building) or sparse (e.g., grassland). Compared with a indoor scene, the height of each region (defined by the maximum z coordinate) is different. Another challenge is that the partition can easily separate the object (e.g. car, building) into different parts in different regions. So the network cannot directly learn the whole geometrical information for most objects. Figure 14 shows some visualization of the partitioned scenes.

Figure 14: Part of a building (left) and part of a parking car (right).

As a compensation, in the training, we partitioned the data with a 50% overlap in both width and length.

To validate the hypothesis that PointNet can handle small-scale point cloud segmentation task, we first train and test PointNet on a small outdoor scene with only 2 million data points. The whole scene was split into 9801 regions, 8801 for training and 1000 for testing. Surprisingly, with only 25 epochs, PointNet achieves **81.5%** for an overall accuracy. However, we should also point out that the data preprocessing time is a bottleneck. In addition, considering the evaluation is based on the same scene data, which is unlikely happening in real-life problems (different terrains).

4.2 PointNet++

4.2.1 Motivation and Idea

In parallel to **PointNet** it was then decided to also explore the modified version of **PointNet** aptly named **PointNet++**. The original work does not capture well local structures, but with the extensions proposed in Qi, Yi, et al. 2017, the point cloud is partitioned into overlapping regions by using a distance metric. Much like convolutional neural networks, the algorithm is able to extract local features; such local features are grouped into large features and processed to abstract to higher level features. This process is then repeated for the entire point set.

Figure 15 shows the architecture of the network, where N refers to the number of points per sample, d is the number of spatial dimensions (x, y, z) and C is the number of feature dimensions, in our case $C = 3$ ('R, G, B'). Note that after the sampling and grouping the output are $N' \times K \times (d + C)$, where each group corresponds to a local region and K is the number of points in the neighborhood of centroid points.

Figure 15: PointNet++ architecture (extracted from Qi, Yi, et al. 2017).

4.2.2 Experimental Setup

Testing strategy The performance of PointNet++ model for semantic segmentation of the given point cloud is evaluated based on following key

points:

- Sensitivity of the results on the point sampling: different point grouping strategies may affect the segmentation, especially when dealing with strongly non-uniform point distributions.
- Class bias: a metric that respects minority classes for evaluating the performance.

PointNet++ Data Sampling

Two data sampling approaches are tested, *KDTree* and pre-processing the data into sample blocks.

KDTree: In the first approach the point cloud data is loaded from *csv*-files and subsequently structured using a *KDTree* with leave size $k = 10$. The tree is saved in *pickle*-format for faster loading in future runs. Samples are constructed from the *KDTree* with 10000 points. To reduce memory but keep the sample dimension of around 3 m radius, the density is reduced by down-sampling randomly to 4096 points.

Considering memory constrains and time per iteration, the batch size is set to $batch_size = 4$ and the number of points for convolution is defined by $K = 32$. Table 1 gives an overview of all parameters.

Table 1: Parameters for data sampling using a *KDTree*

Parameter	Variable	Value
Leave size	k	10
Points per sample	N	10000
Reduced points per sample	$N_{reduced}$	4096
Batch size	$batch_size$	4
Points for convolution	$nsample$	32

Pre-sampled block data: As the previous approach is very time consuming due to loading of the *csv*-files and building/loading of the *KDTree*, a second approach is considered in which the data is pre-sampled into blocks and directly saved as *numpy*-objects. The pre-processed data blocks can be efficiently loaded and directly used as samples which significantly reduce the computing time.

Here, we partition the data into blocks with horizontal dimension of $4\text{m} \times 4\text{m}$. This results in around 6000 points per block. From each block a sample consisting of $N = 4096$ random points is extracted. Batch size is set to 8 for training and 16 for validation. Points for convolution is defined by $K = 32$. Table 2 gives an overview over all parameters.

Table 2: Parameters for the pre-sampled block data

Parameter	Variable	Value
Block size (m)	<i>block_size_input</i>	4
Points per sample	N	4096
Batch size	<i>batch_size</i>	8 (train), 16 (validate)
Points for convolution	K	32

Multiple training-validation tests with different batch sizes and point groupings are carried out. Single-scale grouping (SSG) is implemented which means that a constant size of points is grouped during the convolution process between layers.

4.3 SuperPoint

SuperPoint proposed by Landrieu and Simonovsky 2017 was chosen as, in theory, it allows to greatly reduce the dimensionality of the problem at the stage of deep learning and should work well with large point clouds.

4.3.1 Motivation and Idea

The main motivation for this approach arises from the scale of the data. Point clouds of small areas can easily achieve several millions of points. Larger scenes (block of city, city) can reach billion. Direct end-to-end learning of such datasets becomes intractable.

The SuperPoint graph representation aims to split the semantic segmentation problem into 3 separate problems of different scales (Figure 16).

1. First, the point cloud is partitioned into geometrically simple clusters, called superpoints. Each superpoint is assumed

Figure 16: Illustration of SuperPoint (extracted from Landrieu and Simonovsky 2017).

semantically homogeneous and thus the problem of semantic segmentation of point cloud boils down to semantic segmentation of smaller number of superpoints.

2. The relations between superpoints (superedges) can be calculated from the distance-based adjacency graph. Superpoints, together with superedges, result in superpoint graph. It is possible to assign each superedge a richer feature vector based on the statistics of initial adjacency graph.
3. The graph of superpoints is significantly smaller than the initial point cloud representation and the segmentation of its nodes can be learned with graph convolution algorithms.

4.3.2 Implementation details

The original repository description proposes to

1. Partition of point cloud into superpoint graph (SPG)
2. Deep learning SPG

Partitioning

The pipeline for partitioning is as follows:

1. For each point, take neighbourhood as k_nn_geof nearest

neighbours and calculate 4 geometric features (linearity, planarity, verticality, scattering) out of 3 main eigenvalues of the points covariance matrix. A heuristic formula was tested to choose k_{nn_geof} : $k \approx 1.5d$, where d is the flat density of the point cloud (mean number of point in $1 \sim m^2$). The typical value of k_{nn_geof} for the data provided was 1000. This results into **feature file**.

2. Build the adjacency graph G_{nn} using $k_{nn_adj} = 10$ nearest neighbours.
3. Run cut-pursuit algorithm written in C++ to partition the points into superpoints. The important parameter here is $reg_strength$ which controls the finesse of the resulting partition. We used the value $reg_strength = 1$ which produced reasonable result.
4. Aggregate the connections between superpoints into superedges features. This results into **superpoint graph file**.

The glue parts of the pipeline (building kd-tree for knns and calculating the edge statistics) are written in python and introduce large memory overhead. For example, we found out that running the procedure for *part-5* dataset (25M points) requires at least 40Gb of RAM.

All parts except for cut-pursuit algorithm can be rewritten so they do not require for the whole point cloud to be in memory since the functions need only the neighbourhood of the point.

With the given time restriction, we decided to split the data into patches of $\approx 100 \times 100$ m with 20 m overlap (6-10M points). Each segment was digestible for the partitioning algorithm and was taking around 20 min of CPU time.

Analysis of superpoint partitioning

The partitioning with parameters $k_{nn_geof} = 100$, $k_{nn_adj} = 10$, $lambda_edge_weight = 1$, $reg_strength = 1$ results into the following superpoint graph:

The upper bound for accuracy in this graph was calculated as 94%, which confirms that the chosen parameters are reasonable for the data provided (assuming that each superpoint receives the label corresponding to the majority of the points).

Figure 17: Left: superpoint clusters show oversegmentation. Right: original labels.

4.4 KPCConv

4.4.1 Algorithm description

Thomas et al. 2019 introduced a convolution operator for point clouds. Such operation works in the 3D points domain, i.e., continuous and non-Euclidean. This KPCConv module is proven effective in point cloud classification, part segmentation and point cloud semantic segmentation. However, as the point size used in the paper experiments is smaller than ours, we expect the results to differ. Figure 18 below describes a KPCConv layer.

As shown in Figure 18, KPCConv exploits neighbouring points to extract features. Similarly to 2D convolution, a weight is assigned to each neighbouring point, based on the distance to a kernel point in this case.

Figure 18: KPConv layer (extracted from Thomas et al. 2019).

Finally, an MLP is used to aggregate the information producing new features.

The final architecture employs multiple KPConv layers for the encoding of the network and then few MLP layers to classify the points. Between each layer the points are subsampled to broaden the locality of the features. Furthermore, skip connections are used to improve overall performances.

4.4.2 Experimental Setup

The SenSat dataset is loaded on a KDTree, allowing a extraction of subset of the overall cloud at runtime. The radius of each sub-cloud is fixed and is a hyperparameter.

Point clouds are subsampled with a regularized function that distributes the subclouds sampled so that they are evenly spaced. Each point contains three XYZ coordinates as values and RGBZ as features. The latter Z feature is set in the absolute coordinate system for the experiments and weighted relative for the rest of the experiments.

Dataset is initially subsampled at 10 cm resolution for most experiments and 25 cm resolution for the experiment with the larger kernel and subcloud size. More parameter settings can be found in Table 3.

Table 3: KPConv parameter setting

Parameter	Value
Points for kernel convolution	15
Initial subsampling	0.1
Subcloud radius	5.0
KP Extent (Radius of convolution)	1.0
KP Influence	"linear"
convolution_mode	"sum"
optimizer	SGD with momentum
learning_rate	1e-2
lr decay	0.1**(1/100) at each epoch
momentum	0.98
number of epochs	500
batch size	10

4.5 RandLA-Net

RandLA-Net is an efficient and lightweight neural architecture that directly infers per-point semantics for large-scale point clouds. RandLA-Net is not only up to 200x faster than existing approaches on large-scale point clouds, but also outperforming state-of-the-art semantic segmentation methods on both Semantic3D and SemanticKITTI benchmarks.

4.5.1 Introduction

Most existing approaches can only handle small-scale point clouds during the training by relying on expensive sampling techniques or computationally heavy pre/postprocessing steps. The key to the approach is to use random point sampling instead of more complex point selection approaches. Although remarkably computation and memory efficient, random sampling is not without cost, because prominent point

features may be dropped by chance and it cannot be used directly in existing networks without incurring a performance penalty. To overcome this, RandLA-Net introduces a novel local feature aggregation module to progressively increase the receptive field for each 3D point, thereby effectively preserving geometric details. RandLA-Net is able to directly process large-scale 3D point clouds in a single pass, without requiring any pre/post-processing steps such as voxelization, block partitioning or graph construction.

4.5.2 Network structure

This network follows the widely-used encoder-decoder architecture with skip connections. The input point cloud is first fed to a shared MLP layer to extract per-point features. Four encoding and decoding layers are then used to learn features for each point. Lastly, three fully-connected layers and a dropout layer are used to predict the semantic label of each point. The main architecture of this method is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 7. The detailed architecture of our RandLA-Net. (N, D) represents the number of points and feature dimension respectively. FC: Fully Connected layer, LFA: Local Feature Aggregation, RS: Random Sampling, MLP: shared Multi-Layer Perceptron, US: Up-sampling, DP: Dropout.

Figure 19: RandLA-Net architecture (extracted from Hu et al. 2019).

As shown in Figure 20, the core part of this method is the local feature aggregation module. For each 3D point, RandLA-Net firstly introduces a **local spatial encoding (LocSE)** unit to explicitly preserve local geometric structures. Secondly, RandLA-Net leverages **attentive pooling** to automatically keep the useful features from local neighbourhoods. Thirdly, RandLA-Net stacks multiple LocSE units and attentive poolings as a **dilated residual block**, greatly increasing the

effective receptive field for each point. Finally, by stacking multiple local feature aggregation modules and random sampling layers, RandLA-Net can process large-scale point clouds efficiently. In addition, note that all these neural components are implemented as shared MLPs, and are therefore remarkably memory and computation efficient.

The LocSE architecture is as follows:

Figure 3. The proposed local feature aggregation module. The top panel shows the location spatial encoding block that extracts features, and the attentive pooling mechanism that weights the most important, based on the local context and geometry. The bottom panel shows how two of these components are chained together, to increase the receptive field size, within a residual block.

Figure 20: LocSE architecture (extracted from Hu et al. 2019).

4.5.3 Experimental Setup

As RandLA-Net can handle large-scale point cloud data efficiently, all the data are used for training and testing. The details are discussed in the results. During training and testing, we feed a sub point cloud cropped from the whole point cloud to the network on the fly each time. The batch size is set to 4 during training and 16 during testing. Adam optimizer is used with default parameters. The initial learning rate is set as 0.01 and decreases by 5% after each epoch. The number of nearest points K is set as 16.

4.6 ConvPoint

4.6.1 Introduction

Another baseline method (partially) tested is ConvPoint, standing for continuous convolution for point cloud processing, proposed by Boulch 2019. The method tries to generalise the discrete CNNs by replacing discrete kernels by continuous ones, and does not require fixed number of points as input (Figure 21).

Figure 21: ConvPoint architecture (extracted from Boulch 2019).

It ranked 4th in classification and first large scene segmentation of Semantic3D. The method is claimed to be insensitive to input data size (number of points) and spatial scale. Hence it is suitable for large scale laser scanning or photogrammetric point clouds.

4.6.2 Implementation

Few examples are given in the GitHub repository, including semantic3d. The code was first tested using semantic3d data. Four training data were used for such a test. It was found the training could take very long. For the test, it took around half an hour for each epoch, meaning for 100 epochs it will take 50 hours. Though the training accuracy is steadily increasing, as shown in Figure 22. After only 3 epochs, the overall accuracy is around 95% and IoU about 70%.

Next, the studied data was attempted. Only a subsampled subset of part-5 was tested, including about 1.6 million points. The validation data has

```
(sensat-convpoint) ubuntu@ip-172-31-9-59:~/ConvPoint/examples/semantic3d$ python semantic3d_seg.py --rootdir /sensat-ati/sema3d/dataprepared/train/pointc
--savedir /sensat-ati/sema3d/datatrained
Creating the network...Model with dropout
Done
Create the datasets...Done
Create optimizer...Done
Epoch 0: 100% 1000/1000 [32:21<00:00, 1.94s/it, AA=0.58230, IOU=0.59401, LOSS=3.1142e-06, OA=0.87977]
Epoch 1: 100% 1000/1000 [32:11<00:00, 1.93s/it, AA=0.72402, IOU=0.64485, LOSS=1.6213e-06, OA=0.93590]
Epoch 2: 88% 800/1000 [25:33<05:52, 1.76s/it, AA=0.77698, IOU=0.69779, LOSS=1.3111e-06, OA=0.94730]
```

Figure 22: Training of ConvPoint on the Semantic3D data.

400k points. As expected, the training took a long time, more than one hour per epoch. So only three epochs were trained, as in Figure 23.

```
(sensat-convpoint) ubuntu@ip-172-31-9-59:~/ConvPoint/examples/sensat$ python sensat3d_seg.py --rootdir /sens
cloud --savedir /sensat-ati/sema3d/part-5/datatrained --epochs 3
Creating the network...Model with dropout
Done
Create the datasets...Done
Create optimizer...Done
Epoch 0: 100% 1000/1000 [54:02<00:00, 3.24s/it, AA=0.28564, IOU=0.12015, LOSS=7.6793e-06, OA=0.69091]
Epoch 1: 100% 1000/1000 [54:59<00:00, 3.30s/it, AA=0.33786, IOU=0.27313, LOSS=5.3364e-06, OA=0.77327]
Epoch 2: 1% 7/1000 [00:26<1:02:05, 3.75s/it, AA=0.45699, IOU=0.35119, LOSS=5.2424e-06, OA=0.78686]
```

Figure 23: Training of ConvPoint on SenSat data Part 5.

The data format was simply prepared the same as semantic3d, i.e., data_train.txt and data_train.labels are separated. After three epochs, the OA is around 80% and the IoU is 35%. The results are not considered to be bad as the classes used in the training are the original ones, including 30+0 classes. So the new mapped classes are used for further test. The OA and IoU are 87% and 61% after three epochs.

Then the Part 3 training subset was used for training and the rest of Part 3 for validation. The training OA and IoU are 92% and 64.5% after 100 epochs, respectively, as shown in Figure 24.

```
Epoch 97: 100% 1000/1000 [47:11<00:00, 2.83s/it, AA=0.70208, IOU=0.64183, LOSS=1.6958e-06, OA=0.92067]
Epoch 98: 100% 1000/1000 [47:04<00:00, 2.82s/it, AA=0.70427, IOU=0.64221, LOSS=1.7345e-06, OA=0.91755]
Epoch 99: 100% 1000/1000 [47:07<00:00, 2.83s/it, AA=0.70706, IOU=0.64505, LOSS=1.6900e-06, OA=0.91886]
2019-12-17 06:26:04.132830-Done.
```

Figure 24: Training of ConvPoint on training subset of Part 3.

Unfortunately, the experiment was not finished in time during the challenge, thus no validation result in the part was reported.

5 Experiment results

5.1 Overall results

5.1.1 Quantitative results

Table 4 shows the quantitative results achieved by PointNet, PointNet++, KPConv and RandLA-Net on the validation set. KPConv achieves the highest overall accuracy (OA) and mean IoU (mIoU). But it took almost two weeks for the training. Whereas RandLA-Net achieves similar level of OA and mIoU, with only few hours training. They both outperforms the PointNet methods by a large margin. However, due to the extremely imbalanced data distribution of this dataset, all of these methods achieve poor results on the minority classes (e.g., Construction, water, and Rail). It would be interesting to further investigate the problem of imbalanced data learning. Also, using different loss functions such as Focal loss, Dice loss to solve this problem is worth trying.

Table 4: Validation results of tested methods.

	OA	mAcc	mIoU
PointNet	61.69	25.66	18.89
PointNet++	75.17	34.66	28.61
Vanilla KPConv	91.49	-	63.89
Centered KPConv	93.27	-	65.05
RandLA-Net	90.70	65.15	60.06

5.1.2 Qualitative results and analysis

The following figures show the qualitative results achieved by RandLA-Net and two baseline methods, PointNet and PointNet++. For better illustration, we analyse the results on two different datasets, Part 1 and Part 2. We can see that PointNet achieves poor results on the validation sets. This is mainly because PointNet only learns independent point features without considering local geometric relationships. In addition, the max-pooling operation used for capturing global features discards the majority of information from point features, especially when

processing large point clouds. Compared with PointNet, PointNet++ achieves better results on the datasets. This demonstrated that the local feature abstraction layer used in this method was useful. Thanks to the efficient random sampling and powerful local feature aggregation, RandLA-Net achieved the best results on this dataset. The learned segments were also more consistent and smooth compared with the other two methods.

Figure 25: Input point clouds of Part 1 (left) and results of PointNet (right).

Figure 26: Results of PointNet++ (left) and RandLA-Net (right).

5.2 Detailed KPConv results

To validate the KPConv semantic segmentation architecture, different settings have been tested with the goal of identifying the hyperparameters that could affect results. In particular, the following experiments have been performed:

Figure 27: Ground-truth labels of Part 1 (left) and Part 2 (right).

Figure 28: Input point clouds of Part 2 (left) and result of PointNet (right).

- Vanilla KPConv
- KPConv with no RGB information
- KPConv with weighted Cross Entropy based on class frequency
- Express the point coordinates relatively to the sub-cloud centre.
- Larger kernel radius size and sub-cloud radius while decreasing density with random sub-sampling.

5.2.1 Vanilla KPConv

Vanilla KPConv is used as baseline, since there is no tuning of the hyperparameters for our specific case. In Table 5, results are obtained after different epochs of training. Predictions are shown in Figure 31.

Figure 29: Results of PointNet++ (left) and RandLA-Net (right).

Figure 30: Labels of validation dataset (left) and true colors (right)

We note that compared to RandLA-Net, the network takes a much longer time to converge. Moreover accuracy seems to increase over time even after more than a day of training.

5.2.2 Weighted loss function

The classes distribution suffers from significant class imbalance. One way to attenuate this issue is to weight more mistakes about less frequent classes. These weights are computed as inverse frequency of the labels. Predictions are shown in Figure 32

The results (Table 6) show the weights, used to balance the classes, are not effective. Both the accuracy and mIoU are identical than Vanilla KPConv. Thus, either better weights have to be found, or a more effective

Table 5: Vanilla KPConv: results of different training epochs

epoch	mIoU	Accuracy
epoch 10	29.99	73.27
epoch 149	49.84	87.37
epoch 299	63.44	91.17
epoch 399	63.89	91.48

Figure 31: Vanilla KPConv: predictions at epoch 9 (left) and 399 (right).

approach to balance the classes.

5.2.3 Use of relative coordinates

In addition to the relative locations of the point KPConv accepts the absolute Z value as a feature concatenated to the RGB values (Table 7). The following experiments center the coordinates around the origin of the sub-cloud, and scaled in $[-radius; radius]$. This helps the network to be invariant to the points coordinates. Thus, the model will converge faster

Table 6: Weighted loss function: results of different epochs

epoch	mIoU	Accuracy
epoch 9	29.69	72.46
epoch 149	55.04	87.60
epoch 299	63.74	91.32
epoch 399	63.54	91.58

Figure 32: Weighted loss function: predictions at epoch 399.

Table 7: Results of different epochs

epoch	mIoU	Accuracy
epoch 9	31.39	75.42
epoch 149	54.17	90.44
epoch 299	65.31	93.28
epoch 399	65.05	93.26

and generalize better.

Centering the coordinates and scaling has actually improved the results with respect to the original version (Figure 33). Hence, the network is sensible to changes in XYZ. This experiment provides a starting point for further hyperparameter tuning, and exploration. Although when training for longer time the difference seems to reduce although results seem to depend by class.

It is clear the network is too biased towards majority classes (Figure 34). For instance, as roads are geometrically very similar to ground but less frequent, they are often categorized as ground. Thus, seems to be fundamental to improve the network generalization. A possibility is to force the network to use RGB features more. This can help differentiate between similar geometric classes having different semantics, e.g., roads and ground. However, it would be better to first test whether the network is actually relying on the RGB data.

Figure 33: Relative coordinates: predictions after 9 epochs (left) and 399 epochs (right).

Figure 34: Relative coordinates: Class distribution after 399 epochs.

Training for much longer time it seems that the minority classes are also starting to improve. This might be caused by the fact that it is only now starting to differentiate these classes as it has seen them very rarely.

5.2.4 KPConv with no RGB

The color information is very useful to discriminate between objects. For instance, cars have a very different color than roads in general. However, relying too much on it may drive the network to misclassification. Thus, with the following experiment with the goal is to assess the extent in which the RGB information is actually used by the network.

This experiment shows poorer results than previous settings; both in terms

Table 8: KPConv with no RGB: Results when training for different epochs

epoch	mIoU	Accuracy
epoch 9	28.63	68.44
epoch 149	46.80	86.41
epoch 299	59.27	90.27
epoch 399	60.59	90.72

Figure 35: KPConv with no RGB: predictions after 399 epochs.

of accuracy and mIoU (Table 8). Although the results still show reasonably high accuracy. This means that although RGB does add information the network, it is still able to learn the spatial information from the coordinates alone (Figure 35).

5.2.5 Use of larger kernel and sub-cloud

Looking at previous experimental result, it is in question whether a larger kernel size and sub-cloud is helpful or not. The idea comes from the fact that the features to recognize are significantly bigger than what these networks have been designed for.

Small radius will expose the network to more local geometric cues. While larger kernel may force the network to look for more discriminative features. Hence, theoretically, obtaining better overall results. In the following, a larger kernel and sub-cloud area was tested, but because of memory constraints we had to reduce the initial density parameter. The

mean IoU = 6.408%, and the overall accuracy = 29.693% after 9 epochs (Figure 36).

Figure 36: Larger kernel and sub-cloud: predictions after 9 epochs.

Initial results with a larger kernel size, while keeping the original density, show a reduced accuracy and mIoU. Therefore, the model is not able to exploit, or discriminate, between geometric cues to which it is exposed. A smaller kernel size also decreases performance. Combined these results show that the default settings for this hyperparameter seem to be the optimal ones for our dataset.

5.2.6 Limitations

The experiments above highlight multiple issues. The more relevant one concerns the class imbalance. Multiple solutions are possible, and some of them have been described above. The heavy memory consumption has to be addressed. In particular, the points grouping performed at each layer is heavy memory consuming. Increasing the maximum number of neighbouring points may provide better results. However, at the current state this is not possible. Since the issue is intrinsic with the convolution definition of this specific approach, it may be not suitable for the application at hand.

6 Future work and research avenues

6.1 Evaluation on Cambridge dataset

Our models were trained and validated on different parts of the Birmingham dataset. However, these parts look relatively similar to each other, which means the current approaches were not evaluated on scenarios when the composition of the test area is substantially different. To evaluate the generalization abilities in a better way, we suggest to test the models on the dataset covering central Cambridge.

6.2 Instance segmentation

We have focused on semantic segmentation as semantic labels were available for all points. Due to the lack of supervision over instance data, the only option for instance segmentation is to employ an unsupervised approach.

Two purely unsupervised approaches, an advanced one and a baseline, have been proposed by Wang et al. 2018. Below, the vanilla version is described, based on Breadth-First Search (BFS), then we will describe a more advanced approach called SGPN.

Alternatively, it would be possible to devise a self-supervised approach for instance segmentation. In particular, it is possible to exploit methods used by the satellite image community to extract an instance segmentation, or a bounding box, from the top view of point cloud. Then, these bounding boxes can be augmented with a z components looking at the point cloud. Thus, the generated boxes can be used as supervision for some instance segmentation approach, such as proposed by Yang et al. 2019 or Wang et al. 2018.

6.2.1 Semantic segmentation and Breadth-First Search (BFS)

As the first step, we label the points using one of the selected semantic segmentation methods, for example RandLA-Net. In the next step, all points are considered as seeds and used as starting points for BFS. BFS then finds all neighbouring points that have the same label. If there are

more than a given number of points in a cluster, we consider it as a valid group. Points that belong to multiple clusters are likely to be on the boundaries, so we can assign them randomly across the corresponding groups.

6.2.2 SGPN

Similarity Group Proposal Network (SGPN) is a more advanced alternative to the combination of semantic segmentation and BFS. It first uses PointNet/PointNet++ to extract features of points in the point cloud and then constructs a similarity matrix between pairs of points to create a proposal how to group the points.

6.3 Data augmentation

Data augmentation is a common strategy to improve model robustness to noise and increase generalization. For instance, in order to increase the robustness towards point locations, usually random noise is introduced in the coordinates which is also referred to as *jittering*. Similarly, it is possible to introduce noise in the RGB values, or even drop some of these values. Other augmentation involves random scaling of the XYZ coordinates, or even random rotation of the cloud around the vertical axis. Further augmentation procedure can be used, however, they do not offer benefits for a semantic segmentation task.

6.4 Transfer learning

A potential way to improve performance and accelerate training is to take a model trained on a large-scale dataset and fine-tune it to the new dataset. This is particularly suitable when the new dataset is small and the large-scale dataset is relatively similar to the new dataset. The specific fine-tuning mechanism typically consists of freezing the first n layers and fine-tuning the final two or three layers.

Although some pre-trained models are available for most common 3D point cloud models, the datasets used are significantly different from our data. For instance, both KPConv and all PointNet versions were trained over indoor scene datasets, such as Scannet and S3DIS. Fewer models

are trained over urban environments, however even in this case the data distribution was significantly different than the one in SenSat dataset. Therefore, we have decided not to pursue this research avenue for now.

7 Team members

Alphabetical Order *by family names*

- **Tarek Allam:** Tarek is a 3rd year PhD student at the Centre for Data Intensive Science in UCL. His research broadly focuses on development of time-series classification algorithms for Astrophysical transient events. He contributed to the investigation of using the PointNet++ method and assisted with the implementation of this using PyTorch for application to SenSat data as well as helping with writing up methodology.
- **Ondrej Bohdal:** Ondrej is a first-year PhD student in Data Science at the University of Edinburgh. His research focuses on developing new meta-learning methods to learn how to solve few-shot learning problems across different domains. Ondrej was the facilitator for the project and worked on writing parts of the report.
- **Nanqing Dong:** Nanqing is a first-year Ph.D. student in Computer Science at the University of Oxford. His research focus on machine learning and quantum computing. He contributed to this report on implementing data preprocessing and PointNet (PyTorch) on small partition size, evaluating and visualizing the results, and writing parts of the report.
- **Ivan Erofeev:** Ivan is a postdoctoral researcher in the School of Biological Sciences at the University of Edinburgh. His research focuses on computational biophysics of cell cortex. He contributed to the project by investigating the SuperPoint approach and provided the results of ConvPoint.
- **Qingyong Hu:** Qingyong is a second-year Ph.D. student in the Department of Computer Science at the University of Oxford. His research focuses on computer vision, 3D scene understanding, and

also machine learning system. He contributed to this report by working on the PointNet, PointNet++, KPConv and also RandLA-Net, both implementing these approaches and conducting comparative results for these methods.

- **Julian Kuehnert:** Julian holds a PhD in Geophysics. He recently graduated from the *Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris* (IPGP), France. His research focuses on the simulation of seismic waves generated by rockfalls on real topography using the 3D Spectral Element Method. He contributed to the project by implementing a PyTorch PointNet++ algorithm for the SenSat data and writing parts of the report.
- **Pauline Maury Larivière:** Pauline is a machine learning engineer at Sensat, and has a BSc in Microengineering. She has also recently completed her MSc in Microengineering with a specialisation in Robotics. Her research focuses on semantic and instance segmentation both in 2D and 3D UAV data. She contributed in this study by providing scripts for the experiments with Superpoints Semantic Segmentation.
- **Luca Morreale:** Luca is a first year PhD student in Computer Science at University College London (UCL). His research concerns generative models for unstructured 3D data, e.g., point clouds and meshes. Luca contributed to the project working on the KPConv model, both concerning the experiments and the report.
- **Mukharbek Organokov:** Mukharbek is a Ph.D. in Astrophysics and has recently graduated from the University of Strasbourg (Sept '19). His research at CNRS focused on the search of correlation between different multi messengers in Astronomy (neutrinos, gamma-rays, etc). As a member of DSG, Mukharbek has been working on point cloud semantic segmentation using Superpoint Graphs (SPG) and ConvPoint frameworks.
- **Chenfu Shi:** Chenfu is a third-year PhD student in Bioinformatics at the University of Manchester. He contributed to this project by working on the KPConv model, both exploring empirically the multiple capabilities, summarizing the results obtained and finally providing visualization of the results.
- **Wen Xiao:** Dr Xiao is an University Research Fellow at Newcastle University. His research interests lie in the integration of artificial intelligence, computer vision and robotics, with photogrammetry, laser scanning and remote sensing, applied to urban and natural environments. He is the PI of this DSG challenge.

References

- Boulch, Alexandre (Apr. 2019). "ConvPoint: continuous convolutions for point cloud processing". In: arXiv: 1904.02375. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1904.02375>.
- Hu, Qingyong et al. (2019). "RandLA-Net: Efficient Semantic Segmentation of Large-Scale Point Clouds". In: arXiv: 1911.11236. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1911.11236>.
- Jordan, Jeremy (2018). *Evaluating image segmentation models*. URL: <https://www.jeremyjordan.me/evaluating-image-segmentation-models/> (visited on 01/30/2020).
- Landrieu, Loic and Martin Simonovsky (Nov. 2017). "Large-scale Point Cloud Semantic Segmentation with Superpoint Graphs". In: arXiv: 1711.09869. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1711.09869>.
- Qi, Charles R., Hao Su, et al. (2017). "PointNet: Deep learning on point sets for 3D classification and segmentation". In: *Proceedings - 30th IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR 2017* 2017-Janua, pp. 77–85. DOI: 10.1109/CVPR.2017.16. arXiv: 1612.00593.
- Qi, Charles R., Li Yi, et al. (2017). "PointNet++: Deep hierarchical feature learning on point sets in a metric space". In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 2017-Decem*, pp. 5100–5109. ISSN: 10495258. arXiv: 1706.02413.
- Thomas, Hugues et al. (Apr. 2019). *KPConv: Flexible and Deformable Convolution for Point Clouds*. arXiv: 1904.08889. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1904.08889>.
- Wang, Weiyue et al. (Dec. 2018). *SGPN: Similarity Group Proposal Network for 3D Point Cloud Instance Segmentation*. DOI: 10.1109/CVPR.2018.00272. arXiv: 1711.08588.
- Yang, Bo et al. (June 2019). *Learning Object Bounding Boxes for 3D Instance Segmentation on Point Clouds*. arXiv: 1906.01140. URL: <https://github.com/Yang7879/3D-BoNet>. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1906.01140>.

A List of all labels

<i>Original</i>		<i>Remapped</i>	
#	Class label	#	Class label
0	Unclassified	0	Unclassified
1	Ground_bearRock	1	Ground
2	High Veg Individual Trees	2	High Vegetation
3	Construction Stockpiles	3	Construction
4	Commercial Buildings	6	Buildings
5	Construction_Material laydown	3	Construction
6	Construction_Structure	3	Construction
7	Construction_Temp_Buildings	3	Construction
8	Fence	11	Walls
9	Misc_Bridge	7	Roads
10	Parking Lot	1	Ground
11	Rail_Others_mostly boxy objects	5	Rail
12	Rail_Railway tracks	5	Rail
13	Residential buildings	6	Buildings
14	Road_Main Roads	7	Roads
15	Road_Minor Streets	7	Roads
16	Sports Facilities-Track-Field	1	Ground
17	Street Furniture_Benches	8	Street Furniture
18	Street Furniture_Bollards	8	Street Furniture
19	Street Furniture_Lamp posts	8	Street Furniture
20	Street Furniture_Other	8	Street Furniture
21	Street Furniture_Road signs	8	Street Furniture
22	Street Furniture_Traffic light	8	Street Furniture
23	Vehicles_Cars	9	Cars
24	Vehicles_Lorries	10	HGV
25	Vehicles_Plant-Machinery	10	HGV
26	Wall	11	Walls
27	Footpath-Cycle Path	7	Roads
28	Vehicles_Bikes	12	Bikes
29	Street Furniture_Traffic cones	8	Street Furniture
30	Water_canals	13	Water

turing.ac.uk
@turinginst